

ISic0428

I.Sicily inscription 0428

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.16

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 233

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

- 1.
2. [Co]rneli · Herm[---]
3. [Co]rnelia · Epinice · con[iugi]
4. cum quo vixit ann[---]
5. et liberi utrorumqu[e][---]

Apparatus

Text from CIL

Translation

Commentary

Second fragment still to be identified in museum stores.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491656

EDCS 21900490

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7148 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 680

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Photo J. Prag